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Women Ownership and Participation in Urban Land Development in Urban Sokoto, North-Western Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study examined women ownership and participation in urban land development in Sokoto Metropolis. The population of the study were all urban women selected using purposive and simple random sampling from the twenty four wards of the urban area. Data for the study were obtained from the records of building plan approvals made from 2000–2023 by Sokoto Urban and Regional Planning Board (SURPB). Additionally, structured questionnaire was administered on 840 purposively sampled women across the metropolis. Descriptive statistics and ratios were used for data analysis. The study revealed that majority of the sampled women were married young and medium aged adults. It was found that majority of them obtained only primary and Islamic education. Significant number of the women were housewives with low to medium income status. The study revealed that the commonest means of access to land in the study area is inheritance from close relatives. The number of landowners among the sampled women were low as a result most of them currently do not participate in any form of land development activity. The study revealed that income and age of a woman are two most critical factors significantly influencing land and property ownership and participation by women in the study area. Effect of education is yet to be seen despite improvements in the number of women accessing formal education recently. It was also discovered that complex family relations enhanced by socio-political and cultural practices influence actual control and participation of women in land /property development. The study concluded that these practices combine with low income and lack of awareness prevent women from land ownership in the study area. Therefore, it recommends that Sokoto State Government should emphasis continuing female adult education and equitable access to resources such as skills training/acquisition to enhance access to income earning productive activities particularly for married women.

Keywords: urban land development, women, ownership, participation

1.0 INTRODUCTION

In recent years, women's land and property rights have received considerable attention within the United Nation System and other regional associations. Thus the Global Platform for Action emanating from the World Conference held in Beijing in 1995 acknowledged that women's right to inheritance and ownership of land and property shall be recognised. Studies has shown that access to and benefits from public productive resources is an issue that affect both male and female in most societies, but women were more marginalized compared men (Oshikoya and Ifediora, 2022; Dorcas, 2021). Similar studies in Nigerian, revealed that both men and women own land theoretically, but in reality it was only a small percentage of women that own land and property outright. Most of them have joint ownership with their male partners, often husbands, or acquire land rights through inheritance or customary systems. Women are

also involved in land acquisition, purchasing building materials and in hiring professionals and artisans often alongside their partners. With regards to urban land ownership and development the situation that emerged showed that women were generally marginalized with regard access to urban land (Onibokun, Famoriyo and Akanji, 1995; FAO, 2015).

There are many cultural practices in Nigeria, particularly in northern Nigeria that can restrict women's mobility, access to information, and participation in processes related to property development others included poverty, lack of education, and limited access to financial resources can further restrict women's involvement in urban property development. Additionally, where pressure on land is intense, rapid urban growth, socio-economic and political changes, the plights as well as rights of women and other less privileges were often relegated to the background These problems prevent them from creating sustainable income to access land. Thus there is need to examine the weather women in the study area own land and the extent to which they participate in urban land development. This study examines the socio-economic barriers on the path of women ownership and their participation in land development in Sokoto Metropolis.

1.1 Aim and objectives

The aim of this study is to examine the level of women access to and participation in land development in Sokoto urban area. The specific objectives are:

- (a) to identify the different methods of access to land in the study area
- (b) To find out the level of women participation in urban land development in the study area.
- (c) To investigate the benefits and factors influencing women participation in urban land development in the study area.

2.0 METHODOLOGY

2.1 The study area

Sokoto is the capital of Sokoto State of Nigeria, it is situated at the north west of the confluence of the Rima and Sokoto Rivers (plate 1). This area is located between latitude 12⁰ and 14⁰ N longitude 4⁰ and 6⁰ E (Benna Associates, 1985 and Mamman, 1999). This area has been defined by Sokoto Urban Regional Planning Board (SURPB) as that which is described by a 16km radius centred on the Old Race Course. The area was further extended later to include several critical outlying villages that have a socio-economic dependence upon the town of Sokoto. This "region" or the inner close-settled zone is about 960 square kilometre in area (Benna Associates, 1985). Administratively, this area falls within six Local Government jurisdictions, namely Sokoto North, Sokoto South, Dange - Shuni, Kware and Wamakko (Danmalam, 2010).

Plate 1: Sokoto Urban Area

Source: Geography Department UDUS

2.2 Sampling procedure and sampling size

The population of the study is the sum of the female population of the four LGAs selected for the purpose of this study, they include Sokoto North, Sokoto South, Wamakko and Dange Shuni LGAs. The four LGAs were divided into twenty four political wards. Three wards were randomly selected from Sokoto North and South while one ward each was purposively chosen from Wamakko and Dange Shuni LGAs. Stratified random sampling was used where each of the four local government area was considered as a stratum.

Three wards were randomly selected from Sokoto North, South LGA while one ward were chosen from Wamakko and Dange-Shuni LGA respectively. From these wards unit areas were randomly selected by balloting as study sites and five households were selected randomly from each unit area. Based on the above only female respondents were selected from each household (any senior female member of the house were chosen). To get the sample size for the study, Yamani (1967) statistical formula was employed as shown below:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where N represents population size

n represents minimum sample size

E represents the degree of error expected (0.05)

At the end eight hundred and forty (840) women were selected as sample for investigation. This was allocated using Proportional Allocation Formula (PAF). The documentary information was obtained from records of building plans approved Sokoto Urban and Regional Planning Board (SURPB). The data was presented and analysed by the use of descriptive statistical tools such as tabulations, frequency distributions tables, percentages, ratio while chi-square was used to determine the influence of age, level of education, occupation and economic status on women's property ownership.

3.0 RESULT AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Socio-economic profile of the respondents

The sampled population were aged 20 – 25 to 46 years and above. From the information in Table 2, it was found that majority of the respondents were middle aged women, followed by a large proportion who were aged 32 – 38 years of age, while those respondents aged 20 – 25 years were the least. Majority of the respondents were above 25 years of age, but were mostly below 46 years. This indicates the predominance of young adult women in the sample. As regards marital status, most of the sampled respondents were married, more than half were married at the time of this study while more than a quarter were divorced. Widows and singles were the least among the sampled respondents (Table 2.).

Majority of the sampled respondents had some form of education as shown in the (table 2). A large proportion of the respondents (48.1%) had only Islamic schooling system. Those who have tertiary or post-secondary education were indeed few (7.2%). The study revealed different activities as the main occupation the women in the study area (Table 2). The largest proportion of the respondents (42.3%) revealed that they were full time housewives they do not engage in any form of income earning activity. On the other hand a small proportion of the respondents revealed that they were engage in formal employment in the public sector and its associated institutions. Women who were housewives and at the same time engage in informal petty trading/handwork and buying and selling constituted about one-third of the women, petty trading is the single largest income earning activity engage by women in the area using child labour. The least were those respondents who engaged in formal business and other contracting jobs while none of the respondents were found in any form of agricultural employment or building construction industry in the study area. It was observed that men dominate most of the income earning activities. Men dominated the formal sector employment which provide a strong source of additional income which means greater earnings that have direct bearing to the socio-economic status of an individual as well as access to other income producing assets.

Information from table 2 shows that less than one-third of the women felled within the first income group, then about one-eighths of the sample were found in the second least income group, while less than one-sixth of the women felled within the third income group. Few of the sampled women (3%) were found in the fourth and fifth income categories of the sample. Majority (more than 50%) of the women revealed that they earned less than N50, 000. The study revealed that large proportions of the respondents (38.9%) did not indicate any specific income, this category did not specify their income. The money they normally use is provided by their husbands for family expenses. Although many of the respondents revealed that they do participate at one time or the other in informal saving among women (Adashi) out of the little family expenditure. Majority of respondents were low income earners while many of them did not revealed any specific earning, with regards to personal and independent income. This is because they do not engage in any income earning activity or trade.

Table 2: Socio - Economic Profile of the Respondents

Age	Frequency	%
20 – 25	75	8.9
26 – 31	200	23.8
32 - 38	230	27.3
39 – 45	115	13.6
46 and above	220	26.1
Total	840	100
Marital status		
Married	498	59.2
Divorced	109	12.9
Widowed	141	16.7
Single	92	10.9
Total	840	100
Years of schooling		
Islamic education	210	25.0
Primary School	325	38.6
Secondary school	152	18.0
Tertiary Education	102	12.1
University	51	6.0
Total	840	100
Occupation		
Full time Housewife	346	41.1
Housewife c/servant	184	21.9
Housewife/trader	209	24.5
Business / politics	101	12.0
Total	840	100
Monthly earning		
Below - 20,000	191	22.7
N21,000 - 30,000	159	18.9
N31,000 - 40,000	105	12.5
N41,000 - 50,000	35	4.1
Above -N51,000	26	3.0
No specific income	324	38.5
Total	840	100

Field survey, 2023.

3.2 Means of access to land in the study area.

Land in Sokoto metropolis is mainly used for residential, commercial, farming, public and non-public land use as well as for light industrial activities. The different means of land access to land are inheritance, leasing, outright purchase and gift as well as statutory grants by State government (Table 3.). Some of the respondents revealed that they purchase the land from the land agents/dealers and relatives. However, few of the respondents revealed that they acquired plots through the state government allocation. It was observed that most of the women who acquired land grants were either civil servants or were in party politics. Inheritance which is the dominant method is facilitated by religious factor, because of the practice of Islamic Law of distributing inheritance. The law provides an inheritance system that enabled men/women who are heirs' to a deceased person to acquire his/her properties. But despite the above religious law, culture, attitudes as well as complex and intricate family/gender relations has far reaching influence on who took ownership of which land/property among male/female heirs. The study revealed that the most prevalent method of access to land in the study area was inheritance, purchase, leasing and public grant, while gift was the least (Table 3).

3.3 Types land and property own by women

This study revealed that majority of the respondents do not own any land or property, while only one third of them indicated that they owned plots of land (Table 3). This is followed by those who owned personal

house, house for rent and commercial property. Personal house and commercial property are the most dominant types of properties owned by women (Table 3). Those who indicated owning personal houses were actually occupying them with their families. Commercial properties were basically shops most of which were located on the front sides of the residential houses. Sizes of land within the urban area differ considerably from one area to another as well as the economic strength of the owner. Size of land area occupied by a property within the commercial area and inner city (Birni) tends to be smaller when compared with that of G.R.A and Suburb of the metropolis.

3.4 Methods of land management by women

There are various ways through which women land/property owners manage their properties. The respondents revealed these methods in this manner, self, husband, relations and commissioned agents (Table 3). A proportion of the women revealed that they assigned one of their relatives to manage the land on their behalf, about one third of them indicated that they assigned their husbands to manage the properties while only few of the respondents were in full control of their property themselves. This study revealed that majority of women land owners prefer to use close associates to assist them with the issue of their properties. This is an indication that women land management activities is indirectly through men, because few of them directly control their land. Thus, most of the decisions concerning their land/properties are mostly taken by men on their behalf.

Table 3: Means of access, types and method of land management by women

Method of land acquisition	Frequency	Percentage
Inheritance	174	82.8
As gift	04	1.8
Leasing	11	5.1
Purchase	14	6.6
Government allocation	09	4.2
Total	212	100
Type of property owned		
Plot of land	15	2.2
Personal house	70	10.6
Commercial property	92	14.0
House for rent	35	5.3
None	443	67.6
Total	655	100
Management Method		
Self	19	8.8
Husband	72	33.9
Relatives	102	48.1
Using an agent	19	8.9
Total	212	10

Field survey, 2023.

3.5 Women Participation in urban Land Development in Sokoto

The Participation in land development by gender was measured from the number of applications and approvals made for building construction within the metropolis for 30 year period (1981 to 2010). Applications seeking approvals to build comes from both those who were granted land allocations by the state government as well as land and properties acquired through other means of acquisition / access to land such as inheritance and outright purchase.

The time span was divided into five year periods (table 4.15). In the first period out of every twenty seven approved construction plans only one was secured by a woman, this was followed by gradual downward trends for men in the subsequent years that saw an increased in the proportion of women seeking to build. This continued up to the fifth period when the ratio between male and female approved building plans

reached its lowest levels (18:1). This was followed by an increased in the gap between male and female approvals (26:1) from 2006 to the year 2010. Therefore, the number of women landowners seeking approvals to develop land was higher in the past twenty five years than in the recent five years (2006-2010)

Generally the table showed that the number of women seeking approval to develop land was low when compared to those of men. For examples out of 85847 approved building plans only 4.1% of this figure was actually approved for women land owners. Even with the recent burst in residential and commercial construction activities across the metropolis women are still lagging far behind.

Table 4. Number of building plan approvals 1981-2010

Years	Total Applications	Male Applicants		Female Applicants		Male/Female Ratio
		Number	% of total	Number	% of total	
1981-85	11437	11040	96.5	397	3.4	27:1
1986-90	13303	12811	96.3	492	3.6	26:1
1991-95	7208	6933	96.1	275	3.8	25:1
1996-00	13755	13218	96.1	537	3.9	24:1
2001-05	29812	28294	94.9	1518	5.0	18:1
2006-10	9332	8991	96.3	341	3.6	26:1
Total	84847	81287	95.8	3560	4.1	

Sokoto Urban and Regional Planning Board, 2010.

3.6 Factors influencing women’s access to and participation in land development

Four factors outlined namely: age, education, occupation, and income are considered to be the primary influence on land ownership in the study area (Table 7). In the opinion of the respondents, men dominated both economic and other resources. Ownership of these resources gives an individual better access to land. In agreement with the finding of this study, NCWS (2000) reported that women in Nigeria have insignificant control of the decision making bodies and economic power.

3.7 Age and women’s access to and participation in land development

With regard to age, the findings of the study revealed that majority of the young women aged 15-25 years were without land, with only 10.3% found to be in possession of land in that category. It was noticed that access to land by women increases with age (Table 7), with majority (91.4%) in the category of aged 46 and above having access to land. The result of the chi-square test shows that age significantly affects land ownership as the chi-square value of 185.5 was significant at 0.01 levels (Table 7). Thus we conclude that the older a woman, the more likelihood of her having land or property ownership. This is contrary to the opinions expressed by the sampled respondents in table 4.21. This is because many of the women landowners might have inherited land from their late parents, spouses or relatives.

Table 5. Age and woman’s access and participation

Age	Have Land		Have No Land		Total
	No	%	No	%	
18 – 28	8	10.3	70	89.7	78
29 – 39	40	15.3	222	84.7	262
40 – 49	59	26.6	171	74.4	230
50 &above	105	91.4	10	8.6	115
Total	212(30.9%)		473(69%)		685

Field survey, 2021. χ^2 cal = 183.5** χ^2 tab = 11.34 df, = 3 **Significant at p<0.01

3.8 Education and women’s access and participation

With regard to educational attainment of the respondents, the sampled women were divided into four categories (Table 8). The first category consisted of those with only traditional Islamic education. In this group less than half of the women (47.7%) had land, while slightly more than half of the women have no land. The second category consists of those with primary education in addition to the religious education, majority in this category had no land, while only 18.6% of the respondents indicated owning land. The trend here shows that level of women’s education as a factor generally regardless of type (Islamic and western education) had direct have no impact on women’s land ownership. The study revealed that those women who owned land were mostly those who were 46years and above which correspond to those with Islamic or primary education only. Majority of those with western education had no land or landed property, they also correspond to younger women aged below 50years (Table 8). Therefore, when this issue is considered on the basis of type, we can conclude that the level of formal western education has very little effects on land ownership among women. Majority of women with land or property have only traditional Islamic education. This is the reason for the high chi-square value of 46 which is significant at 0.01 level.

Table 6. Education and women’s access and participation

Education	Have Land		Have No Land		Total
	No	%	No	%	
Islamic	156	47.7	171	52.3	327
Primary	38	18.6	166	81.4	204
Secondary	09	9.0	91	91.0	100
Tertiary	09	18.4	40	81.6	49
Total	212(31.1%)		468(68.8%)		680

Field survey, 2021 χ^2 cal = 46** χ^2 tab = 11.34 df, = 3 **Significant at p<0.01

3.9 Occupation and Women’s access and participation

On the basis of occupation, the respondents were grouped into four. The first group consisted of full time housewives, where majority (64.5%) of them do not owned any land or property. Land ownership was found to be highest among women in business and politics with 83.0%, while land ownership was least among women in petty trading with only 21.2%. (Table 9). This study indicated that occupation of women affects their access to and ownership of land as also confirmed by the Chi- square value of 103.7 which is significant at 0.01 level (Table 9).

Table 7. Occupation and women’s access and participation

Occupation	Have Land		Have No Land		Total
	No	%	No	%	
Fulltime-Housewife	103	35.5	187	64.5	290
Civil Servants	31	23.2	103	76.8	134
Petty traders	44	21.2	163	78.8	207
Business/politics	34	83.0	7	17.0	41
Total	212(31.5%)		460(68.4%)		672

Field survey, 2021 χ^2 cal = 103.7** χ^2 tab = 11.34 df,=3 **Significant at p<0.01

3.10 Income and women’s ownership and participation

With regard to income earnings among the sampled women, the respondents were divided into six income groups. Significant proportion of the respondents revealed that they have no specific income at the time of the survey. The largest income group were those who earned less than N10, 000 monthly (Table 10). The study revealed that land and property ownership increased with level of income (Table 10). The chi-square value of 133.3 is significant at 0.01 levels showing that land ownership differ among different income categories. It is mostly those with large income that think about long-term investment in land. In some instances, women trade-off their rights in order to enjoy kin protection and support in the event of

spousal troubles. Also exchange is very common among family members, where female heirs exchange landed property for movable property and liquid cash. Sometimes gender issues influence sharing of inheritance in land and property where male heirs tend to be given preference with regards to residential houses and undeveloped land.

Table 8: Income and women’s land ownership

Income Level	Have Land		Have No Land		Total
	No	%	No	%	
Not Specified	72	25.0	217	75.0	289
Less -10,000	38	20.0	152	80.0	190
N11000 -20,000	32	38.8	48	61.0	80
N21000 -30,000	53	50.5	52	49.5	105
N31000 -40,000	8	80.0	2	20.0	10
Above-N41,000	9	81.0	2	19.0	11
Total	212 (30.9%)		473 (69%)		685

Field survey, 2023 χ^2 cal = 133.3** χ^2 tab = 15.09 df = 5 **Significant at p<0.01.

3.11 Benefits of ownership and participation in land to women

Various reasons were given by the sampled respondents to support their view that personal land / property is also important to women like men. Majority (93.7%) of the sample women indicated that a personal land or property is also important to women, while less than one tenth had contrary opinion (Table 11). This respondents revealed two paramount reasons for the value of land to women, this is because land is a source social security and source of income. They also revealed that marriage and social relations are so precarious today this leave women sometimes in a hard situation. Therefore, they feel that they need a sort of social security nets which land can serve as such. As regards the latter (as sources income) from which they can engage in home based productive activities from their personal land. This can give them some degree of financial autonomy from relations/husbands. The others saw personal land ownership as a valuable asset that can be held for future need and the fact that their personal property frees them from dependence on others and can also avoid unhappy or problematic relation (Table 11). This shows that women in the study area perceived land ownership in different ways and this depends on their personal experience with regard to spousal and family relation. Evidence suggests that many of those who opted for land control and social security might have previous unhappy marriage/family relations that propelled them to strive for a land or house of their own, or they have a number of dependants that require personal care.

Table 9: Benefits of land ownership and participation to women

Benefits of landownership to women	Frequency	%
Social security	201	23.9
Source of income	205	24.4
As an asset	107	12.7
Financial independence	155	18.4
Family obligations	172	20.4
Total	840	100

Field survey: 2023

3.12 Barriers to woman’s ownership and participation in land development

Some of the problems women land owners were facing in managing their properties includes; seclusion, cheating by relations and gender issues (Table 11). Less than half (42.4%) of the respondents women indicated that societal perceptions and attitudes with regard to women who lives in their own houses is the

main problems they were facing. Slightly less than one third of the women showed that cheating on the part of those (relatives) they entrusted with their properties is the second problem. This was followed by the issue of seclusion which could not allow them to know exactly what is going on with regards to their land/property. About one tenth of the sample indicated all the problems outlined above. From these findings it can be deduced that women who owned land/ property experience one problem or the other particularly if they were married. Any transaction in land or property is mostly done indirectly through family relation or husbands (Table 11). Therefore, these problems should be expected to limit their desire to acquire land and housing.

Table 10: Barriers to woman’s land ownership and participation

Barriers	Frequency	%
Seclusion	174	20.7
Cheating by relatives/spouses	191	22.7
Inadequate resources	243	28.9
Cultural practices	111	13.2
Insecurity	121	14.4
Total	840	100

Field survey, 2024

4.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This research examined the influence of gender in access to and actual ownership of land. In view of the findings from the data analysis above any prospects of enhancing women’s access to land must take cognizance of some important socio-cultural values. What is needed therefore, is change in practices that have been identified as reducing women’s land rights. In general, the study found trends which are similar to what has been reported in some of the research literature in some aspects, example women in the study area have poor socio economic conditions, along with poor participation in land development activities. Though, it is probable that low income women generally fare worse off than most men in terms of participation in development activities and access to opportunities. There is a need, therefore, in current attempts at improving the situation of women, to focus not just on creating access and opportunities for women, but particular on creating access and opportunities for low income women because of their existing condition. Women in the study area actually are at bottom of monetary earnings, that they earn much less to nothing. The extent and magnitude of the above factors actually affect the whole process of development. Therefore, any effort to empower and increase their access to basic productive resources should begin with education and economic empowerment. In view of the findings of this study the following recommendations should be considered as part of the efforts to enhance women’s access to productive resources, land in particular:

The girl-child education policy of the state Government must be given more emphasis, through incentives to female students and the State government should make secondary education compulsory for every child, particularly females. This to be done through involvement of local governments and traditional institutions. Adult literacy/skills acquisition centres should be establish for married women who were unable to attend formal schooling. These centres should be run by local female teachers/instructors. Financial institutions (Urban Development Bank and Federal Mortgage Bank) can extend soft loans to low income women to acquire and personal land/property. The State Ministry for women affairs together with women organizations should undertake enlightenments programmes targeting women on the benefits acquiring income producing properties.

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